

Tackling cyber threats with automatic decisions and reactions based on machine-learning techniques

Mattia Zago¹, Víctor Manuel Ruiz Sánchez², Manuel Gil Pérez¹, Gregorio Martínez Pérez¹

¹Departamento de Ingeniería de la Información y las Comunicaciones

²Cátedra SAES Laboratories

University of Murcia, 30.100 Murcia, Spain

Email: {mattia.zago, victormanuel.ruiz, mgilperez, gregorio}@um.es

Abstract — Despite the important effort dedicated to maximise the security of network infrastructures and the services provided on top of them some major cyberthreats, such as botnets, persist. If classic botnets are nowadays difficult to track due to the amount of devices that may potentially be subjugated, at the dawn of the 5G era, with an even increased number of devices powered by ultra-wide broadband, this problem seems to be even more relevant. In this context, the paper at hand describes a system designed considering the integration of multiple machine-learning algorithms with some other technologies like Software-Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Virtual Functions (NFV) that are usually being considered as enablers in 5G. The intention of this system is to analyse, detect and react against existing and new coming cyber threats, including botnets.

Keywords — Machine learning, cyber threats, automatic detection, automatic reaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Next-Generation 5G communications will change current IP networks regarding the number and heterogeneous type of connected and communicating devices. In such a scenario, the network security and specifically the automation of security management tasks becomes a crucial aspect.

Along with other tasks in detection, network-traffic classification and automatic reactions are nowadays offering relevant research challenges. For that reason, our objective is to advance the current state of the art of these topics by deploying a security framework that can be used in both current IP networks and new coming 5G networks implementing Software-Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Virtual Functions (NFV) technologies for operation. To achieve that, our architecture features a set of Machine Learning (ML) powered modules that automatically adapt (to provide flexibility to zero-day attacks), classify and analyse (to improve the overall knowledge) network traffics.

In machine learning, on one hand, unsupervised problems are devoted to finding patterns and structures, mainly to increase the knowledge of unlabelled data; supervised problems are, on the other hand, dedicated to modelling and explaining of labelled data. In between, there exists the semi-supervised class of problems, where only a part of the data is labelled, either by human experts, during the data acquisition or at generation time.

Our proposed architecture combines the best of each approach trying to create a scalable detection and reaction framework willing to decrease the error rate as well as increasing the efficiency in terms of computational resources. Each algorithm cited in our model is initially implemented via the standard libraries made available by the Scikit-Learn framework¹.

This paper is organised as follows. The next section provides an analysis of the related work. Later, section III provides an overall view of the architecture, presenting in subsections III.A and III.B a detailed explanation of the algorithms chosen and the motivation behind them. And finally, we highlight our conclusions and our proposed future works in section IV.

II. RELATED WORK

With the increasing effort in traffic concealing, security attacks are not anymore identifiable using obvious static features such as application ports, payload analysis, etc. Machine learning offers a promising alternative. In fact, it has been successfully applied several times to approach the network security problem. Pellegrino et al. [1] proposed a novel automata-based learning model for short-term interaction pattern detection. Chen et al. [2] applied the physics gravitational law to the data space, obtaining a solid semi-supervised learning model for internet traffic. Mai and Park [3] analysed the performances of the three most popular clustering techniques. Chen et al. [4] successfully applied Flexible Neural Networks as classifier, providing a comparison with notable Bayesian, rule-based, tree-based and function-based classifiers. Villegas Alejandro et al. [5] used a genetic approach to Feature Selection prior to classifying network traffic with a C4.5 decision tree. And although Mekky et al. [6] focus refer to generic malwares, their random forest classifier represents an excellent example of removing background network flows. Finally, Singh and Bijalwan [7] and Buczak and Guven [8] provide a survey of botnet detection techniques.

Besides machine learning techniques, statistic-based models can provide similar result by extrapolating spectral features or aggregating basic metrics to highlight anomalies [9].

A. Datasets

Datasets are the primary input of any machine learning technique. Even being a critical element to foster the work in this

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¹ Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in {P}ython, <http://scikit-learn.org/>

TABLE I FEATURES USED BY OUR MODEL IN COMPARISON WITH THE CURRENT STATE OF THE ART.

Selected Features	Description	[1] Pellegrino et al.	[2] Chen et al.	[3] Mai et al.	[4] Chen et al.	[5] Alejandre et al.	[6] Mekky et al.
STIME, LTIME	Record start or last time	X					
FLGS	Flow state flags						X
SADDR, DADDR	IP address	X					
PROTO	Transaction protocol	X		X			X
SPORT, DPORT	Port number			X			X
STOS, DTOS	TOS byte value						
STTL, DTTL	TTL value.						
DIR	Direction of transaction	X					
SINTPKT, DINTPKT	Interpacket arrival time (ms)		X				
SJIT, DJIT	Jitter (ms)						
STATE	Transaction state						X
TCPRTT, SYNACK, ACKDAT	TCP connection setup time						
SMAXSZ, DMAXSZ, MAXSZ	Maximum packet size				X		X
SMINSZ, DMINSZ, MINSZ	Minimum packet size				X		X
DUR	Duration of a flow	X	X			X	
RATE, SRATE, DRATE	Packets per second			X		X	
SPKTS, DPKTS, PKTS	Transaction packet count	X	X			X	
SBYTES, DBYTES, BYTES	Transaction bytes	X	X		X	X	X
SAPPBYTES, DAPPBYTES, APPBYTES	Application bytes		X		X	X	

^a The S-prefix indicates a source feature, the D-prefix indicates a destination feature and the absence of these prefix indicates an aggregated feature computed over the flow.

field, there are two main issues with currently existing network datasets.

- Recording real-world network flows is, *per se*, a simple task. However, the real problem is legal as storing and publicly sharing real network data requires authorizations and legal permits.
- There exists a multitude of botnet malwares spread across the cyber-world. Most of them are comparable in terms of periodicity, i.e. bots must contact a command and control server to remain active.

For such reasons obtaining a dataset that can legally provide enough data for machine learning training is still an open challenge.

In 2014, García et al. [10] analysed eight different datasets publicly available at that time, aiming to promote the research and the creation of a new comprehensive dataset. The resulting dataset, named CTU-13, however, due to legal issues does not include the full PCAP trace but only a reduced network flow.

Under these circumstances, and as our research work on 5G networking is based on a higher number of metrics extracted directly from raw 5G network traces, we finally decided to rely on another well-known botnet dataset: the ISOT Botnet dataset [11]. The ISOT dataset is a mixture of botnet traffic (both HTTP and P2P) generated by two machines infected with either Storm or Waledad malwares. Along with this malicious traces, the ISOT dataset features background traffic generated by the Ericsson Research’s Traffic Laboratory.

Creating a publicly available network dataset with both normal, background and botnet PCAP raw traces remains a major challenge.

B. Dimensionality Reduction

Aside from the dataset challenge, learning models suffer another major issue, which is related with finding the best representation of the provided data. TABLE I presents a list of features that our model considers, plus the comparison with the previously cited related works. Higher dimensionality implies higher resources consumption, and thus a balance is needed to avoid performance deterioration while preserving data consistency. This problem is known in machine learning as Curse of Dimensionality, and to solve it there are two possible approaches: Feature Selection and Feature Extraction.

On one hand, Feature Selection focus on filtering the redundant and irrelevant variables creating a smaller feature subset without adversely affecting the data consistency reliability. For reference, Najafabadi et al. [12] present a complete comparison of Feature Selection algorithms applied to the intrusion detection challenge.

On the other hand, Feature Extraction techniques focus either on maintain the representation capabilities or enhancing discrimination capabilities while extracting new variables rejecting and combining the original feature space. A valid example of such techniques is presented by Cano et al. [13], which proposed a Pareto-based multi-objective genetic programming algorithm that retrieves a new feature subspace with a lower dimensionality from a given feature space.

In Section III.A.2 we will describe our proposed Dimensionality Reduction module.

III. ARCHITECTURAL SCHEMA

Our proposed architecture, as presented in Figure 1, is divided into two main blocks:

- the semi-supervised pre-processing module, which provides an accurate filtering at the cost of being unable to detect previously unknown attacks; and,
- the management and reaction module, which combines supervised learning techniques with trained handlers, i.e. highly specific managers with several capabilities, ranging from a DPI (Deep Packet Inspection) module deployment to countermeasure through policy enforcement.

Section III.A illustrates our proposed model for the semi-supervised pre-processing module, while Section III.B presents how we handle such information for generating any reaction policies.

A. Flow pre-processing and first classification

In the first module, the Filter requires a set of traffic flow collected by either an SDN Controller or a generic monitor module. Such flows are received conforming to the Cisco's NetFlow format, i.e., a sequence of one or more packets travelling between two hosts using a given protocol (e.g. TCP, UDP, ICMP). For detection purposes, a NetFlow message is usually characterised by seven unique keys: the source IP address, the destination IP address, the source port, the destination port, the Layer 3 Protocol, the Type of Service and the Input Logical Interface. Nevertheless, our prototype discards the unused keys (source port, type of service and Input Logical Interface) and consequently regroups the flows accordingly. Furthermore, the model at this stage relies on the information provided by the network monitor for what concerns the layer 3, 4, and 7 protocols in use in each given flow.

Each flow is composed by features, a fixed but arbitrary number of metrics such as instant measures (e.g. the number of packets) and aggregated measures (such as the average waiting time between subsequent packets). Those metrics values are not suitable for direct usage as their domains are intrinsically different, ergo not directly comparable; therefore, a

standardisation module maps each flow data into a vector of floats such that the mean value and the variance of the whole set are respectively zero and one. From now on, we will refer to such standardised values as features.

1) Rule Based System

Since machine-learning-based anomaly detection is rather computationally expensive, our approach employs a rule-based filtering mechanism to sensibly improve the performances.

Such filtering module, based on a classic rule-based analyser, lacks the capabilities needed to detect unknown activities; nevertheless, it allows to sort whitelisted traffic or previously known threats. Once a flow matches any given rule, a previously generated reaction policy is activated and sent to the Action Enforcer module (see Section III.B). Alternatively, the flows are sent to the machine learning pipeline (described in Section III.A.2).

2) Machine Learning Based System

As previously described in Section II.B, the number of features collected is too high to create an efficient learning module; hence a Dimensionality Reduction module is required and used in our approach to prevent any problem related to the Curse of Dimensionality.

The best suitable algorithm for such a module in the context of 5G networking is still under investigation in our team, and a full comparison in terms of interpretability, stability, accuracy and scalability is intentionally left as future work; for such a reason, it is referred as dimensionality reduction of the data in this paper with independence of the final method chosen. This reduction is currently assumed to be done by a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) until that investigation is completed.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the flows are then analysed by a machine learning module called Class Sorter with the purpose of performing unsupervised pattern recognition. This module, implemented as a Random Forest, attempts to recognise temporal patterns in the processed data, offering the flexibility needed to detect variations of known attacks. Each leaf is connected to a specific and highly trained handler. Such handlers represent the decision core of our framework, and their functionalities are described in Section III.B.

Fig. 1. Architectural Schema

Undoubtedly, the extensive definition of such unique handlers for any possible flow requires a lot of work. For such reason, an ultimate handler has been defined as the *worst-case scenario*. This handler performs generic unsupervised clustering to suggest possible schemas to a human expert.

The chosen algorithm for the Class Sorter, the Random Forest, has been selected based on the empirical results over the ISOT Botnet dataset. The conducted experiment was performed comparing four classifiers: a Random Forest, a K-NN, a Naïve Bayes, and a Logistic Regression. The evaluation in terms of typical machine learning performance scores such as precision, recall or F1 score has been performed using a stratified 10-fold cross-validation; such results are available in Table II.

TABLE II CLASSIFICATION RESULTS FOR THE ISOT DATASET

Method	AUC	CA	F1	Precision	Recall
Random Forest	0.997	0.985	0.985	0.985	0.985
K-nearest neighbors	0.994	0.984	0.984	0.984	0.984
Naive Bayes	0.937	0.831	0.834	0.842	0.831
Logistic Regression	0.914	0.830	0.830	0.831	0.830

B. Management and Reaction

A handler is by design a black-box submodule, which receives as input a labelled flow and has two possible outcomes:

- reclassify the flow (i.e. adding a subclass or report a classification error); and,
- generate a reaction policy (i.e., a collection of atomic actions or countermeasures apt to react).

Additionally, a handler may include an extra entry point used by a reinforced learning model. Such input, if available, may be considered while establishing the appropriate response to the given network state.

Once a reaction policy has been given by any of the prior systems, the Action Enforcer module will choose the best way to implement the necessary set of actions to enforce it. It may also return a reward that reflect the effectiveness of the adopted reaction. Such reward can be also provided in our design by the handler.

This complex solution permits the agility required in order to be aligned with the requirements of the new Moving Target Defence (MTD) paradigm, which “seeks to develop game-changing capabilities that dynamically shift the attack surface” [14]. To reach such ambitious objective, our framework heavily relies on the new capabilities offered by SDNs and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). Specifically, whenever a reaction policy is issued to the Action Enforcer, it can notify the SDN controller to deploy the correspondent mitigation plan.

For example, once the Class Sorter tags a network flow as suspicious, a deep packet inspector can be deployed to investigate and determine any evidence of malicious activity. Our proposed model could, in fact, work as an advanced decision module in a mature environment such as the one proposed by Machado et al. [15], hence enabling network self-protection capabilities.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In the context of automation of network security tasks, our proposed framework provides an elegant vertical solution for both classification and automatic reaction processes. Machine learning algorithms can indeed improve the precision as well as the efficacy of such modules without losing essential properties such as scalability or accuracy. As current work, a complete and meticulous comparison between the existent dimensionality reduction techniques and classification algorithms is being accomplished in the context of the proposed solution. We are still working on obtaining as many datasets as possible to test the model with the broadest possible scope. Once we know the best dimensionality reduction technique and have enough data for testing, we should be able to determine which classification algorithm works better for each type of flows, thus adjusting the proposed system accordingly.

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